

Supplemental Material

Supplementary Material Figure S1. Population index values for Mallards in the Netherlands based on an integrated population model. The index value 100 is based on the population size of the year 1990 and corresponds to approximately 350,000-500,000 breeding pairs. Error bars around point estimates show the corresponding 95% Bayesian credible intervals (CRI). Points in black depict the unobserved index values while red points depict the observed values.

Supplementary Material Figure S2. Estimates of daily survival rate for fledging Mallard ducklings in the Netherlands based on an integrated population model. Duckling survival increases with duckling age until they fledge at eight weeks old.

Supplementary Material Figure S3. Linear regressions between IPM estimates of reproductive rate with (A) clutch size, (B) nest success, and (C) duckling survival rate for Dutch Mallards for the years 2003-2020. Reproductive rate is defined as the number of new adult females produced per adult female per year, and duckling survival as the probability that a duckling reaches 56 days of age. Shaded areas represent the 95%-confidence intervals of the regression lines

Supplementary material Table S1. Estimates of vital rates for Mallards in the Netherlands for the years 2003-2020, as approximated with an integrated population model. For each parameter the mean, standard deviation, and the 95% Bayesian credible interval (CI) of the posterior distribution are given. Random effects (σ) give the standard deviation of the error around vital rate mean estimates, while fixed effects (β) indicate the logit coefficients of the linear time trends per vital rate across the study period. The $\beta_{\text{duckling survival}}$ parameters are the logit coefficients describing the relationship between duckling survival and duckling age.

Parameter	Mean	SD	2.5% CI	97.5% CI
Nest success	0.38	0.01	0.36	0.40
Clutch size	8.16	0.05	8.06	8.25
Egg hatch rate	0.96	0.00	0.96	0.96
Duckling survival	0.18	0.02	0.14	0.23
Adult survival	0.71	0.03	0.67	0.76
Recovery rate ⁽¹⁾	0.11	0.01	0.09	0.13
Population growth rate ⁽²⁾	0.98	0.01	0.97	1.00
Reproductive rate ⁽³⁾	0.40	0.05	0.30	0.50
$\sigma_{\text{nest success}}$	0.31	0.08	0.20	0.49
$\sigma_{\text{clutch size}}$	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.06
$\sigma_{\text{adult survival}}$	0.14	0.12	0.01	0.44
$\sigma_{\text{recovery rate}}$	0.23	0.17	0.01	0.62
$\sigma_{\text{population index}}$	4.03	2.68	0.17	9.43
$\beta_{\text{nest success}}$	0.11	0.08	-0.05	0.28
$\beta_{\text{clutch size}}$	-0.01	0.01	-0.03	0.01
$\beta_{\text{duckling survival, 2018}}$	2.58	0.46	1.80	3.56
$\beta_{\text{duckling survival, 2019}}$	2.23	0.34	1.63	2.95
$\beta_{\text{duckling survival, 2020}}$	1.55	0.16	1.26	1.87

⁽¹⁾ The average probability that a banded adult bird is recovered dead and reported; ⁽²⁾ The average change in population size from one breeding season to the next; ⁽³⁾ The average number of female fledglings produced per female per breeding season.

Supplementary Material Table S2 Data from Eygenraam (1957) used to derive estimates of historical duckling survival to fledging age (D) for 1951-1954. D per average female is calculated by multiplying D per successful female by the probability that a female successfully produces at least one fledgling (0.765) during a breeding season (Eygenraam 1957).

Year	Mean brood size (day 1) for a successful female	Mean brood size (week 7-8) for a successful female	D for a successful female	D for an average female
1951	10.69	6.05	0.57	0.43
1952	10.34	6.91	0.67	0.51
1953	9.65	6.61	0.68	0.52
1954	9.22	6.42	0.70	0.53

Supplementary Material Table S3 Estimates of adult survival (S) and recovery rate (r) for Dutch Mallards using the Dead Recoveries (Seber parametrization) model in program MARK. We fitted models where S and r were constant (.) or variable throughout the years (t). We additionally tested models where S was different the first year after banding as compared to later years. Models with S(t + age) are not depicted in the table due to negligible Akaike Weights.

Model	Akaike Weight	Estimate of S	Standard Error of S	Estimate of r	Standard Error of r
{S(.) r(.)}	0.56421	0.7282708	0.0256361	0.1041752	0.0078953
{S(age) r(.)}	0.39069	0.7107891	0.0316828	0.10578	0.0084286
{S(.) r(t)}	0.02213	0.734098	0.0263207	0.2463167	0.1388838
{S(age) r(t)}	0.0189	0.7131368	0.0330258	0.2289618	0.1296907
{S(t) r(t)}	0.00404	0.522599	0.2564003	0.139645	0.103649
{S(t) r(.)}	0.00002	0.6259753	0.1709855	0.1027348	0.010196
Weighted Average	1.0	0.7204497	0.0290898	0.1104498	0.0136917

Supplementary Material Table S4 Model selection table for the duckling survival model where duckling survival was modeled as either a function of duckling age, year, both, or neither. Model performance is indicated by the Deviance Information Criterion (DIC). Model selection was performed using the duckling survival model of the IPM and was with JAGS using 50,000 iterations.

model	DIC	ΔDIC
Age + Year	10351.86	0
Age	10362.47	10.6143
Year	10740.41	388.548
Null	10742.9	391.043